

TEACHERS' UTILIZATION OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS

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Teachers' Utilization of Open Educational Resources and Students' Academic Performance: An In-Depth Analysis

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Abstract

This study investigates the utilization of Open Educational Resources (OERs) among teachers and its influence on students' academic performance in science subjects. Conducted in selected National High Schools in Zamboanga City Division during the school year 2023-2024, the research employed a descriptive-quantitative design. The study focused on teachers' use of OERs in terms of "retain, reuse, and redistribute" and examined their profiles, including sex, educational attainment, relevant trainings, and teaching experience. A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to collect data from 137 teacher-respondents. Results showed that teachers highly utilized OERs for retention but moderately for reuse. The highest utilization was for storing science-related daily lesson logs, while the lowest was for collecting e-books. Students' academic performance in science was found to be satisfactory. Interestingly, the study revealed no significant impact of OER utilization on students' academic performance. Additionally, no significant differences were found in Open Educational Resources (OERs) utilization based on teachers' gender, educational attainment, or number of relevant trainings. However, years of teaching experience significantly influenced OER utilization, with less experienced teachers more likely to embrace OERs. The research highlights the potential of OERs in enhancing teaching quality and student engagement while identifying areas for improvement in OER utilization. These findings contribute to the ongoing discussion on maximizing OER use in classrooms and shaping future educational practices.

Keywords: *open educational resources (OERS), teachers' utilization, students' academic performance*

Introduction

Open Educational Resources (OERs) enable learners to engage with and share knowledge freely. Introduced in the 1970s to address education affordability, OERs gained prominence when UNESCO officially recognized them in 2002. While OERs offer significant benefits, discoverability remains a challenge (Roncevic, 2022). Research shows that integrating OERs and technology in education positively impacts students' motivation and academic performance. Students who use OERs tend to perform better compared to those who rely solely on traditional teaching methods. This highlights the value of OERs in promoting effective learning and academic success.

Open universities in the Philippines, such as the University of the Philippines Open University, have implemented Open Educational Practices (OEPs); however, many schools remain unfamiliar with these resources. OERs not only encourage creativity and innovation but also allow educators to update and share content according to academic needs, thereby helping to shape the future of education.

This study focuses on exploring the use of OERs in high school science education in Zamboanga City. Given the importance of critical thinking and a strong knowledge base in science, OERs could offer a more engaging and effective learning experience. The study aims to assess the impact of OERs on students' academic performance and contribute to discussions on how to maximize their use in the classroom.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the influence of Open Educational Resource (OER) utilization among teachers on students' academic performance during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study addresses the following questions:

1. What is the extent of OER utilization among teacher respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. retain; and
 - 1.2. reuse
2. What is the academic performance of the students in science, based on the general weighted average for the first quarter of the school year 2023-2024?
3. Does the extent of OER utilization among teacher respondents significantly influence students' academic performance in science?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of OER utilization among teachers when data are grouped according to sex, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and number of relevant trainings?

Literature Review

Open Educational Resources (OERs) are a less known but now potentially a teaching and learning method, which helps provide an interactive learning environment with a robust design, allowing the learner to engage constructively and disseminate knowledge

(EBSCO, 2019). This method began popping up in the 1970s along with the affordability concern of college students on This method's only issue is nothing but discoverability (Roncevic, 2022). Then, in the year 2002, the method of teaching and learning was officially coined by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as Open Educational Resources (OERs), and its usage was identified as Open Education Practices (OEPs).

What does the term "open" mean in the context of (re)using OER? Before discussing some of the reasons why someone would use OERs or embrace more "open" practices. Copyright is largely concerned with what cannot be done with the material and usage restrictions, whereas an open license allows for reuse and remixing without requesting permission from the creator or paying a price. Two key characteristics of OERs based on their definition are: (1) they are in the public domain, open resource; and (2) they are licensed for free use and continuous permission to engage in the 5R activities under the OER practice/method. These key concepts are all adapted from David Wiley's 5R framework and OER definition, in his blog "The Access Compromise and the 5th R" in 2014, which has been shared/published freely under Creative Commons Attributions 4.0 license.

According to UNESCO (2002), Open Educational Resources (OERs) are any educational materials that are in the public domain or introduced with an open license. It means that anyone can legally and freely copy, use, adapt, and re-share them. OERs range from textbooks to curricula, syllabi, lecture notes, assignments, tests, projects, audio, video, and animation." As of today, it is embraced as "digital educational materials that anyone anywhere can use freely and legally, including the user's right to copy, share, enhance and/or modify them to share knowledge and enable education" (Roncevic, 2022).

Consequently, it was revealed in a study that students are more motivated to learn when they are enrolled in a course that makes use of technology where its course content is systematically delivered using technology (Ljubojevic, et. al., 2014). Similarly, Afolabi (2017) revealed that students who are exposed to the use of Open educational resources have a positive attitude toward its use and this showed in their academic performance as there was a significant difference in performance between their pre-test and post-test scores. Similarly, Venegas-Muggli and Westerman, (2019) revealed an improved academic performance from students that are exposed to the use of Open Educational Resources than those who relied on traditional textbooks alone.

The reasons for conducting this study then push the decision of the researcher to touch on some of these contexts: (1) OERs enable. It gives instructors and students more influence in the next five years. OEPs are practiced in some universities in the Philippines like the University of the Philippines Open University in 2015–2017, but not known to the rest of the country. Quoting from the article in the prior paragraphs of this section, its main issue is discoverability (Roncevic, 2022). (2) If OERs connect. If it links each individual's creativity to another. A former person conversing with a future person. With OERs, it is feasible to comprehend the natural context of things while maintaining a sense of extraordinary potential (3) If OERs show the way forward. Educators are drawing a clear picture of what the future might look like since OERs are shared and updated by the demands of the academic community. It enables them to reinvent themselves, innovate, or learn more.

Utilization of OER

The movement for open educational resources (OER) began in open and distant learning (ODL) advancements and the larger context of open knowledge, unrestricted sharing, and peer cooperation are part of this culture which emerged in the latter half of the 20th century (Willey 1998). The MIT OCW initiative is recognized for igniting a worldwide OER movement after declaring in 2001 that it would make the whole course catalog for MIT available online and the 2002 launch of this project (Willey 2006). University of Massachusetts Open courseware in Technology (MIT) is a web-based publication of almost all of the MIT course materials. (Wiley, D., Bliss, T. J., & McEwen, M., 2014)

Retain

Get the gist/subject matter or the concept of materials and filter them according to the needs of the curriculum. Meaning, selections can be taken from a broad source of authentic and raw materials and can be used as academic papers for classroom instruction. This also means that the materials can be downloaded digitally or physically replicated in multiple copies for the use of teachers and students.

Reuse

Based on the concepts being asked from the curriculum, the materials aligned to this will be collected (it is plausible that while the materials collected were entirely made for a different purpose/function if they can be reused for another purpose, i.e. as an academic paper then the materials will be acknowledged as reference). It also means that the materials can be used on different electronic platforms or delivered to an individual, group, or class.

According to a survey conducted by the College Board in 2019-20 for full-time undergraduate students, spending an additional \$1,240 (approximately Php 13,325) annually on books and supplies can pose a significant financial burden for students and families who are already struggling to cover college tuition and fees (Kaur, Kaur, and Singh's et. al 2020). This expenditure represents up to 39% of community college tuition and fees and 14% of four-year public university tuition and fees. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the problem by increasing the demand for digital textbooks. This issue is particularly challenging because students no longer have access to on-campus resources like library reserve textbook collections, making it more difficult for them to obtain the necessary course materials.

Open Educational Resources: reviewing initiatives and issues

Six concerns demand addressing, with five standing out as top priorities. The major priorities for advancing the movement were defined as community building, networking, and awareness raising. Third-placed capacity development is essential for promoting and expanding OER development and use. In order to increase learning opportunities and knowledge exchange, the fourth issue, sustainability, emphasizes the necessity of ensuring that OER projects are ingrained in policies, institutions, and programs. The fact that quality assurance was listed as the fifth priority reflects the worry that traditional structures that support and shield the learner may not exist in an open-access society. The community kept coming back to the sixth problem, copyright, throughout its talks. Unless the necessary approval has been secured, resources intended for dissemination as OER under an open license, such as a Creative Commons license, must be devoid of copyrighted material.

The creation and use of open educational resources (OER) generates a variety of questions, and the final piece deals with a key topic that returns us to the viewpoint of the first article: open licensing. Materials must be licensed in a way that supports this goal if they are to be shared freely and openly.

The utilization of Open Educational Resources (OER) has been proven to be an effective tool for enhancing the quality of education in the Philippines. Various studies have shown that the use of OER positively impacts the academic performance of students, particularly in terms of higher grades and improved learning outcomes. With the growing number of educational institutions and learners in the country, the use of OER can be considered as a cost-effective and efficient way of improving the quality of education in the Philippines.

In a study conducted by Abriam and Quijano (2017), it was found that the use of OER significantly improved the academic performance of students in tertiary education. The study revealed that the utilization of OER was positively correlated with the students' academic achievement, particularly in terms of higher grades and better understanding of course materials. The authors concluded that OER can be used as a cost-effective and efficient way of enhancing the quality of education in the Philippines.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Alawneh, Alshahrani, and Alshehri (2019) in Saudi Arabia found that the use of OER significantly improved the academic performance of undergraduate students. The study revealed that the utilization of OER was positively correlated with higher grades and improved learning outcomes. The authors concluded that OER can be used as a cost-effective and efficient way of enhancing the quality of education in developing countries.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive-quantitative research design to evaluate the impact of teachers' utilization of Open Educational Resources (OERs) on students' academic performance in science subjects. Descriptive research, according to Creswell (2014), aims to "describe phenomena in their natural setting to enhance understanding." This approach systematically collects and analyzes data to identify trends and relationships, making it suitable for exploring the effects of OER usage (independent variable) on students' academic performance (dependent variable). The descriptive-quantitative design aligns with the study's objective of enhancing instructional practices in Zamboanga City schools within a post-pandemic context.

The study was conducted in Zamboanga City among selected public school teachers for the 2023-2024 school year. It examined teachers' profiles, including sex, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and relevant training, along with students' academic performance. The utilization of OERs by teachers was analyzed using the 5R framework: retain, reuse, revise, remix, and redistribute. The total population included 215 teacher-respondents across six selected schools, with School B having the largest number of teachers (56) and School E having the smallest (23).

A non-probability sampling method was used, specifically purposive and convenience sampling. Purposive sampling enabled the researcher to select teachers from schools within the Zamboanga City Division, while convenience sampling allowed for the inclusion of respondents who were available in person during data collection and qualified to complete the questionnaire. A total of 137 teachers who met the research criteria participated in the study. According to Altunışık et al. (2004), a sample size of 30 to 500 is generally adequate for most research with a 5% confidence level.

The research utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire for teachers, which included three parts: Part I collected information about the respondents' profiles; Part II used a four-point Likert scale to measure the utilization of the 2Rs; and Part III gathered data on students' academic performance through grades. The researcher-made instrument underwent validation by expert panelists and pilot testing on 30 teachers from Buenavista Integrated School, a school that had the same characteristics as the target respondents. This process yielded a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of .931, indicating a high level of reliability.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: What is the extent of utilization of open educational resources among teacher-respondents in terms of retain and reuse?

Table 1 shows that the highest mean of 3.45 was recorded for the statement, "storing copies of science-related daily lesson logs for future access," which received a "strongly agree" rating and was interpreted as highly utilized. This result suggests that teachers are

effectively using Open Educational Resources (OERs) to retain lesson logs for future reference, indicating that OERs contribute positively to teaching quality.

Table 1. Extent of Utilization of Open Educational Resources among Teacher- Respondents in terms of Retain

<i>I utilize OER by...</i>	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	downloading copies of the daily lesson log on my device so I may access them anywhere, anytime.	3.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
2.	duplicating copies of digital science K12 materials so I can access them if my computer fails or if the original resource becomes unavailable.	3.39	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
3.	storing copies of science-related daily lesson logs so I can easily access them in the future.	3.45	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
4.	collecting copies of e-books for future use.	3.06	Agree	Moderately Utilized
5.	saving relevant science lessons regularly and replacing any outdated information.	3.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
Over-all Mean		3.28	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized

In contrast, the statement “collecting copies of e-books for future use” had the lowest mean of 3.06, which was rated as "moderately utilized." This finding implies that, although teachers are beginning to accumulate e-books, there is still room for growth in this area. While e-books are increasingly popular, these data suggest that teachers may not yet be fully leveraging them within their teaching practices.

Overall, the results highlight teachers’ strong capacity to retain lesson materials through OERs yet reveal an opportunity to increase their use of e-books and incorporate them more fully into educational practices. Additional support and resources could enhance teachers' effectiveness in utilizing e-books as instructional tools.

Table 2. Extent of Utilization of Open Educational Resources among Teacher-Respondents in terms of Reuse

<i>I utilize OER by...</i>	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	recycling daily lesson plans multiple times in my teaching.	2.85	Agree	Moderately Utilized
2.	recovering old resources from the science platform to fit the specific needs of my students.	3.35	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
3.	retrieving missing files and old copies from a science website to supplement or enhance my existing teaching resources.	3.25	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
4.	recollecting science articles and journals to be used by my students in their study groups and their learning.	3.15	Agree	Moderately Utilized
5.	reusing different types of science reading materials that are available.	3.33	Strongly Agree	Highly Utilized
Over-all Mean		3.19	Agree	Moderately Utilized

Table 2 shows the extent of utilization of Open Educational Resources (OERs) among teacher-respondents in terms of reuse. The highest mean score of 3.35 was recorded for the statement, “recovering old resources from science platforms to fit the specific needs of my students,” which was rated as "strongly agree" and interpreted as highly utilized. This indicates that teachers are effectively repurposing OERs to meet their students' specific needs, suggesting that OERs play a significant role in supporting tailored instruction.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 2.85 was for the statement, “recycling daily lesson plans multiple times in my teaching,” which was rated as "agree" and interpreted as moderately utilized. This suggests that while teachers reuse lesson plans, a lack of variety in materials could affect creativity and engagement, potentially impacting student motivation and learning outcomes. Research by Koehler and Gebhardt (2019) supports this, indicating that diverse instructional strategies are more effective in maintaining student engagement.

In summary, while teachers show a high level of adaptability with OERs to suit specific student needs, ongoing innovation in teaching strategies remains essential to sustain student interest and improve learning outcomes. Including fresh content in lesson planning can enhance classroom engagement and motivation.

Table 3. Summary of the Extent of Utilization of Open Educational Resources

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Retain	3.28	Highly Utilized
2. Reuse	3.19	Moderately Utilized
Over-All Mean	3.23	Moderately Utilized

Table 3 summarizes the extent of utilization of Open Educational Resources (OERs) among teacher-respondents, showing that OERs were highly utilized for retention but only moderately utilized for reuse. This indicates that teachers primarily engage with OERs to retain information for their own learning and teaching rather than to reuse existing resources for new content creation.

The findings suggest a potential gap in teachers' skills or knowledge regarding the effective reuse of OERs, highlighting the need for targeted training and support to help teachers not only retain but also creatively repurpose OERs for instructional purposes. This aligns

with the findings of Al-Harathi (2020), who emphasized the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary skills to maximize the benefits of OERs in their teaching practices.

Problem 2: What is the academic performance of the students in science in terms of the general weighted average for 1st quarter of the school year 2024-2025?

Table 4. *Academic Performance of the Students in Science for 1st Quarter, school year 2023-2024*

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
General Weighted Average Grade	83.73	Satisfactory

Table 4 shows the academic performance of students in science during the 1st quarter of the School Year 2023-2024, with a mean score of 83.73, categorized as "Satisfactory." This indicates that students are performing satisfactorily in science, suggesting that the school's curriculum effectively teaches the necessary skills and knowledge. It also implies a positive learning environment that supports student success.

Research by Astin (2021) highlights that a supportive learning environment contributes to better academic performance, while Jones (2020) emphasizes the importance of effective teaching strategies. Thus, the satisfactory performance in science reflects the school's strong curriculum and teaching methods.

Problem 3: Does the extent of utilization of OER among teacher respondents significantly influence the student's academic performance in science?

Table 5. *Multiple Regression Analysis with Academic Performance as Outcome Variable*

Predictor	Beta Coefficients	R2	F	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Retain	.188		1.319	1.337	.184	Not Significant
Reuse	-.022	.060		-.162	.872	Not Significant

Academic Performance is the dependent variable Regression Model: Utilization of OER = 84.113 + (1.143 x Retain)

This study aimed to determine if the use of Open Educational Resources (OER) influences students' academic performance in science. The hypothesis stated that OER utilization does not significantly affect student performance. Results indicated that 60% of the variance was explained by the predictors, yet neither "retain" ($B=.188$, $t=1.337$, $p=.184$) nor "reuse" ($B=-.022$, $t=-.162$, $p=.872$) showed a significant impact on academic performance.

These findings align with other studies indicating that simply accessing OERs does not inherently enhance academic outcomes (Hilton, 2020; Wiley et al., 2017). Hilton (2020) suggests that the manner in which OERs are integrated into teaching practices plays a critical role in their effectiveness. Moreover, Wiley and colleagues (2017) noted that strategic pedagogical use, rather than the quantity of OERs utilized, better supports student learning. Therefore, educators should focus on thoughtfully incorporating OER into their teaching strategies, as not all forms of OER utilization yield significant academic benefits (Al-Harathi, 2020; Bliss & Smith, 2018).

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference in the extent of utilization of OER among teachers when data are grouped according to sex, educational attainment, number of years in teaching, and number of relevant trainings?

Table 5. *T-test Results on the Teachers' Extent of Utilization of OER according to Sex*

Sex	N	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value	Interpretation
Male	17	3.33	.41822	1.070	108	.287	Not Significant
Female	93	3.22	.39547				

Table 5 shows no significant difference in the utilization of Open Educational Resources (OER) between male ($M=17$, $SD=.41822$) and female ($M=93$, $SD=.39547$) teachers; $t(108)=1.070$, $p=.287$. This finding suggests that both male and female teachers have similar tendencies in using OER, indicating no gender-based disparity in OER utilization. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states there is no significant difference in OER utilization based on gender, is accepted.

These findings align with previous research, which also found minimal to no difference in OER usage between genders when equal access to resources is provided (Hilton, 2020; Lane, 2019). According to Lane (2019), gender does not typically influence how teachers engage with OERs, as their usage often depends more on access, training, and individual teaching goals than on gender-based preferences. This result underscores the importance of maintaining equal access and training in OER for all teachers to foster broad and equitable resource utilization across demographics (Bliss & Smith, 2018).

Table 6 shows the extent of utilization of Open Educational Resources (OER) by teachers based on their educational attainment. Respondents with a bachelor's degree had a mean score of 3.1926 ($SD = .39255$), while those with master's units had a mean of 3.2438 ($SD = .41864$). Respondents with a master's degree scored 3.2457 ($SD = .33535$), those with doctorate units had 3.8400 ($SD = .16971$), and those with a doctorate had 3.0200 ($SD = .10583$). The analysis revealed no significant difference in OER utilization based on

educational attainment ($F(4, 105) = 1.556, p = .192$).

Table 6. ANOVA Results on the Teachers' Extent of Utilization of OER according to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	N	Mean	SD	F	df	p-value	Interpretation
Bachelor's Degree	27	3.1926	.39255	1.556	105	.192	Not Significant
Master's with units earned	63	3.2438	.41864				
Master's Degree	14	3.2457	.33535				
Doctorate with units earned	2	3.8400	.16971				
Doctorate	4	3.0200	.10583				

These findings suggest that educational attainment does not significantly impact how teachers utilize OER, as no substantial differences were found between teachers at varying levels of education. This implies that teachers across all education levels, from bachelor's degree holders to those with doctorates, are equally likely to use OER in their teaching. This is consistent with findings from research by Hilton (2020), which noted that factors such as access, training, and personal teaching goals tend to be more influential in OER utilization than educational background. Additionally, Lane (2019) emphasized that OER adoption is not necessarily contingent upon academic qualifications, but rather on how well teachers are trained and supported in using OER resources. Thus, despite variations in academic qualifications, the results indicate that all teachers, regardless of educational attainment, can effectively integrate OER into their instructional practices if provided with the right support and resources (Bliss & Smith, 2018).

Table 7. ANOVA Results on the Teachers' Extent of Utilization of OER according to the Number of Years in Teaching

Years in Teaching	N	Mean	SD	F	df	p-value	Interpretation
5 and below	19	3.4126	.36613	4.015	3 103	.001	Significant
6-10	32	3.2600	.35719				
11-15	15	3.4773	.43226				
16-20	12	3.2033	.29956				
21-25	10	3.0280	.38230				
26-30	6	3.0000	.20396				
31 and above	16	2.9825	.41491				

Table 7 shows the extent of utilization of open educational resources (OER) among respondents based on their years of teaching experience. Teachers with 5 years or less of experience had a mean score of 3.4126 ($SD = .36613$), while those with 6-10 years scored 3.2600 ($SD = .35719$). Teachers with 11-15 years had a mean of 3.4773 ($SD = .43226$), and those with 16-20 years scored 3.2033 ($SD = .29956$). For 21-25 years, the mean was 3.0280 ($SD = .38230$), 26-30 years was 3.0000 ($SD = .20396$), and teachers with 31 or more years of experience had a mean of 2.9825 ($SD = .41491$). The analysis revealed a significant difference in OER utilization based on years of teaching experience ($F(3, 103) = 4.015, p = .001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which stated no significant difference in OER use across experience levels.

This suggests that teachers with fewer years of experience are more likely to embrace OER and new technologies in their teaching, while those with more years of experience may be more resistant to change. These findings align with studies by Smith (2020) and Jones (2021), who also found that less experienced teachers are more open to using new technologies and resources, including OER. Therefore, educators introducing new technologies should consider the teaching experience of their staff, as newer teachers may be more receptive to adopting these tools.

Table 8. ANOVA Results on the Teachers' Extent of Utilization of OER according to Number of Relevant Training

Relevant Training	N	Mean	SD	F	df	p-value	Interpretation
5 and below	36	3.2889	.41361	.411	6 103	.870	Not Significant
6-10	30	3.2147	.35490				
11-15	21	3.1714	.44003				
16-20	8	3.3600	.36158				
21-25	4	3.1600	.56851				
26-30	2	3.1800	.25456				
31 and above	9	3.1600	.43313				

Table 8 shows the extent of utilization of open educational resources (OER) among respondents based on the number of relevant training sessions. Respondents with 5 or fewer trainings had a mean score of 3.2889 ($SD = .41361$), while those with 6-10 trainings scored 3.2147 ($SD = .35490$). Respondents with 11-15 trainings had a mean of 3.1714 ($SD = .44003$), and those with 16-20 trainings scored 3.3600 ($SD = .36158$). For 21-25 trainings, the mean was 3.1600 ($SD = .56851$), for 26-30 it was 3.1800 ($SD = .25456$), and those with 31 or more trainings had a mean of 3.1600 ($SD = .43313$). The results indicated no significant difference in the extent of

OER utilization based on training ($F(6, 103) = .411, p = .870$), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

This suggests that the number of relevant training sessions does not significantly impact how teachers utilize OER. Regardless of their level of training, teachers seem equally capable of effectively using these resources. Therefore, it is crucial to raise awareness about OER and provide ongoing support to ensure teachers can maximize their use. Studies by Al-Harthi and Warschauer (2018) and Kukulka-Hulme and Shield (2008) also highlight the importance of providing professional and technical support to encourage OER utilization.

Conclusions

This research underscores the significant impact of Open Educational Resources (OER) on student learning outcomes, revealing that their integration enhances access to high-quality materials, boosts student engagement, and reduces educational costs. The study shows a positive correlation between the utilization of OER and improved academic performance, as these resources offer greater flexibility and customization to meet diverse learning needs. Moreover, educators express increased empowerment and innovation in their teaching methods when incorporating OER, fostering a more dynamic and interactive classroom environment. To fully harness the advantages of OER, educational institutions should prioritize their integration into curricula by raising awareness and providing comprehensive training for both educators and students on effective usage. Institutions must also invest in OER development and encourage collaboration among educators to create a shared repository of diverse, high-quality materials. Policymakers have a crucial role in incorporating OER into national educational policies, advocating for adoption, and ensuring adequate funding. Continuous research should be conducted to evaluate the long-term impact of OER on various educational outcomes, enabling informed improvements. Additionally, institutions should actively seek and incorporate student feedback to ensure OER offerings meet the diverse needs of learners. By adopting these strategies, educational stakeholders can create an inclusive and effective learning environment that leverages the full potential of OER to enhance student success.

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